

Predicting the thermal performance of pulsating heat pipes using artificial neural networks

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Abstract – The present work proposes a promising approach to predict the thermal performance of Pulsating Heat Pipes (PHPs) using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The available database corresponds to 1097 experimental records with nine distinct geometries conceived in the frame of the Clean Sky2 project PHP2. According to the transient data, for 12.5% of cases, PHPs failed to operate in a pulsating mode and instead exhibited conduction behavior. Thus, the proposed approach consists of separating the database into 'Conduction' and 'Pulsation' and training three ANN models. First, a classification model is constructed to predict the operating mode. The F1-score, used to examine the accuracy of this model, resulted in 96.35 % for the pulsation category. Then, a regression model is created for each mode to predict the thermal resistance. The mean relative error of regression models resulted in an acceptable error of 11.48% and 40.93% for pulsating and conduction modes, respectively.

Keywords: Thermal management, Pulsating heat pipes, Artificial neural networks, Classification, Regression.

1. Introduction

Thermal management is a crucial challenge when conceiving conventional aircraft [1]. This challenge is made even harder by electrification due to the high volume of power-embedded electronics that it requires. Optimizing the efficiency of these electric devices results in a drastic increase in heat loads; therefore, solutions are required to limit heat rejection outboard [2]. Using Pulsating Heat Pipes (PHPs) is one of the most promising passive cooling techniques not only in the thermal management aerospace industries [3] but also in renewable energy [4] and microelectronics [5] thanks to their wickless structure, same directional liquid-vapor flow, and shape flexibility compared to the simple heat pipe. Moreover, PHP is an efficient two-phase heat transfer device that can transport massive amounts of heat over long distances with a slight temperature gradient due to phase change phenomena. The heat is transmitted from the evaporator to the condenser by the oscillating/pulsating motion of the two-phase vapor bubble and liquid slug [6]. Because of the complex thermo-hydrodynamics of a PHP, mathematical prediction models are proposed to understand the influence of oscillating/pulsating motions on heat transfer. Therefore, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are among the most appropriate approaches reported to predict the nonlinear behavior and thermal performance of a PHP [7- 10]. However, in the context of PHP devices, most research attempts have dedicated their efforts to the prediction of key design parameters, such as thermal resistance and pressure drop. Moreover, it is worth noting that recently, Loyola-Fuentes et al. [11] were the first to study machine learning algorithms to identify flow pattern transitions in a single-loop PHP system. They classified data into two categories “slug/plug flow” and “semi-annular flow”.

The objective of this study is to provide an effective tool to characterize and optimize PHP in various application synergies. Thus, a database with different PHP geometries and multiple operating points was constructed. This database serves to build surrogate models capable of predicting the thermal resistance of pulsating heat pipes. In previous work, Mouret et al. [12] studied the predictive performance of six machine learning algorithms, including artificial neural networks. Using this model to predict prototypes whose geometry is close to the training ones resulted in a mean relative error of around 30%. The error becomes much more critical (about 80%) on a more challenging prototype (with a very different

geometry). The performance of the trained ANN model could be improved by separating the data based on the dominant operating mode. Two dominant behaviors of the fluid flow inside the capillary tube were identified based on the analysis of the transient data [13] :

- Pulsation regime characterized by a low-frequency domain of the temperature at the evaporator.
- Conduction regime due to the non-confinement of the vapor bubble at high saturation temperatures.

For this reason, three ANN models are presented in this paper. First, a classification model (Model 1) is constructed to predict the dominant operating mode (Pulsation/ Conduction). Then a regression model is created to predict the thermal performance of the PHPs that operate with a dominant pulsation mode (Model 2). Finally, another model is built for PHPs operating with a dominant conduction mode (Model 3); the results of this model, however, are the least important as the dominant conduction mode is undesirable and is to be eliminated when optimizing the efficiency of PHPs for better thermal management.

2. Experimental database

The experimental database was built based on a Design of Experiment (DoE) that uses pseudo-random Halton sequences [14] [15] to ensure a uniformly sampled design space.

The input variables used to implement the mathematical model are divided into operational and design parameters, which determine the thermal performance of PHPs.

The design variables include the internal diameter, the total length, the condenser and the evaporator lengths, as well as the number of U-turns. On the other hand, the operational parameters include the working fluid, the inclinations, the temperature at the condenser, and the filling ratio. The range of the operational variables considered to build the experimental database is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Operational parameters considered for the DoE

Fluid	Filling ratio (FR)	Cold source temperature ($T_{condenser}$)	Pitch (α)	Roll (β)	Heat Load (Q)
-	[%]	[°C]	[°]	[°]	[W]
R1233zdE	40	5	0	0	Starts at 5W and rises until dry-out
R1234zeE	55	20	45	45	
R1234yf	60	35	90	90	

Nine prototypes are thus drawn from the Halton sequence and their geometrical parameters are presented in Table 2. The choice of these prototypes is detailed by Becerril et al. [16] .

Table 2: Geometrical properties of the nine tested prototypes

Prototype	L_{tot} [m]	L_{cond} [m]	L_{evap} [m]	U_{turns} [-]	D_{in} [m]
1	0.186	0.058	0.019	19	0.002
2	0.282	0.164	0.035	21	0.002
3	1.245	0.410	0.067	13	0.001
4	0.818	0.222	0.072	15	0.001
5	0.445	0.227	0.054	17	0.0005
6	0.274	0.127	0.040	11	0.0015
7	0.489	0.248	0.049	17	0.0015
8	0.871	0.260	0.044	15	0.0015
9	1.445	0.303	0.077	11	0.0015

Drawing the geometric parameters along with the operational ones, a series of measurements for different heat loads lead to 1097 data records. Figure 1 presents a picture of the test bench used to test the different PHP prototypes by providing a determined heat load (Q) to the device in testing and reject that same heat load to a chiller. The measures start with a heat load of 5W and increase until dry-out or an evaporator temperature of 90°C is reached. More details about the experiments can be found in Ref.[17].

Figure 1 : A picture of the test bench

3. Methodology

The construction of the surrogate model is based on the following method. The experimental database is randomly split into 90/10 % train and test datasets. First, the model is trained over the train set: its parameters are adjusted to fit the data and minimize the error. The trained model is then tested on the test set. The train/test process is repeated continuously until the results are satisfactory (over the test set).

Because the data is randomly split, the performance of the model depends on the choice of training and test sets. In order to create an effective unbiased model, Cross Validation (CV) is considered. Among all versions of CV, k-fold cross-validation is the most used to fit and assess a model for predictive performance estimation and comparison [18]. In this procedure, the data set is randomly split into k parts or folds, each containing an approximately equal number of data points. The first part is left out for testing, and the remaining $(k - 1)$ part forms the training data. A given model is fit on the training data and then applied to the test set to obtain predictions. The process is repeated, leaving out each k part in turn. In this way, all the data are used for training and testing, but the assessment is honest as no case was used simultaneously in the training and the test sets.

The inputs of the classification and regression models are the eleven geometric and operational parameters sampled in the DoE, except for the heat load converted into a heat flux.

For regression models, the output is the thermal resistance of the PHP, computed from the average of the evaporator and condenser temperatures measured at four different positions:

$$R_{th} = \frac{T_{evaporator} - T_{condenser}}{Q} \quad (1)$$

For the construction of the classification model, the first step is to classify the experimental data into "conduction" and "pulsation" categories. The analysis of the transient data for each record shows that in 12.5 % of cases, the PHP failed to operate in pulsating mode and exhibited dominating conduction behavior. The bar plots in Figure 2a) show the large mass of records that belong to the majority class (Pulsation) and the small number of records spread out to the minority class (Conduction). Therefore, most of the points fall into the pulsating category resulting in a problem of imbalanced data. In other words, there are too few examples of the minority class for a machine learning model to learn the decision boundary effectively.

In order to address imbalanced datasets, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is considered in this study. This data augmentation method consists of duplicating minority class measures, as new examples can be synthesized from the existing samples [19], [20].

Figure 2: Bar plots representing the distribution of data records into pulsation and conduction a) before applying SMOTE and b) after applying SMOTE

According to Chawla et al. [19], SMOTE performs better when combined with the under-sampling of the majority class. Thus, the minor class is oversampled using SMOTE with a ratio of 0.5, while the major class is under-sampled with a ratio of 0.7. The bar plots of the transformed Dataset in Figure 2b) illustrate the increase in the minority class representing 41.2 % of the overall data.

3.1. Prediction Model: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are massive parallel computational models that imitate the function of the human brain. An ANN consists of an input layer, several hidden layers, and a final output layer [21]. Each layer consists of many simple processors called “neurons” linked by weighted connections. Each node output depends only on the locally available information at the node, either stored internally or arriving via the weighted connections[22]. In order to find the output of a neuron, the weighted sum (by the weights of their connections) of all the precedent neurons is computed, and a bias term is added to this sum. This sum is passed through a (usually nonlinear) activation function to produce the output. The result of the neural network can be expressed as the matrix product of each layer.

An ANN model runs based on hyperparameters before the training begins. These hyperparameters include the learning rate, the number of epochs, the batch size, the activation function and kernel initializer of hidden layers, and the number of neurons and hidden layers.

3.2. Evaluation Methodology

After establishing the network, specific evaluation criteria should be used to evaluate the performance of the artificial neural networks [23]. For example, for the binary classification model, given a specific instance, two possible predicted outcomes exist for each instance, as shown in the confusion matrix in Table 3.

Table 3: Confusion matrix applied to the binary classification model (conduction/pulsation).

	Predicted conduction	Predicted pulsation
Actual conduction	True conduction (TN)	False pulsation (FP)
Actual pulsation	False conduction (FN)	True Pulsation (TP)

Therefore, based on these instances, the classification model is evaluated by examining the F1- Score, the precision, and recall of the pulsating class [24]. The Precision metric measures the percentage of truly pulsating categories out of all predicted "Pulsation."

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, the recall metric, also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, measures the percentage of all true pulsation predicted out of the real pulsating category.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

F1-score is the harmonic mean Recall and precision [25]. It measures the quality of the category prediction by combining recall and precision.

$$F_1 score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (4)$$

For regression models, the Root Mean Square Error (*RMSE*) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) are used to assess the performance of the training model. These metrics are given by the following equations:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N (y_{i_{test}} - y_{i_{pred}})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i^N (y_{i_{test}} - y_{i_{pred}})^2}{\sum_i^N (y_{i_{test}} - \bar{y})^2} \quad (6)$$

$y_{i_{test}}$ and $y_{i_{pred}}$ represent the actual and predicted thermal resistance, respectively, while \bar{y} represents the mean value of the actual thermal resistance.

4. Results and discussions

It is essential to determine the appropriate hyperparameters of the ANN hidden layers to ensure the accuracy of the model while avoiding overfitting. Furthermore, because ANN models are intuitive, their optimization requires optimizing the choice of hyperparameters. Therefore, hyperparameter tuning is conducted to study how each parameter affects the performance of the model.

In this paper, the iterative process of selecting the best configurations of hyperparameters is not presented; only the best models it yields are evaluated in this section. A wide range of hyperparameters is tested for the three ANN models (on 5 data folds), and the parameters allowing the best performance for each model are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Optimal hyperparameters for each ANN model

Classification model	Regression Models	
Model 1	Model 2: Pulsation data	Model 3: Conduction data
<u>Hidden layers:</u> number: 2 Number of neurons: [100, 40] Optimizer: Adam (Learning rate: 0.01) Activation function: relu Number of epochs: 1000 Batch size: 8 <u>Output Layer:</u> activation: SoftMax Loss function: categorical_crossentropy	<u>Hidden layers:</u> number: 3 Number of neurons: [20,5,40] Optimizer: Adam (Learning rate: 0.01) Activation function: tanh Number of epochs: 500 Batch size: 8 <u>Output Layer:</u> activation: Linear Loss function: mean squared error	<u>Hidden layers:</u> number: 3 Number of neurons: [40, 20, 100] Optimizer: Adam (Learning rate: 0.01) Activation function: sigmoid Number of epochs: 1500 Batch size: 32 <u>Output Layer:</u> activation: Linear Loss function: mean squared error

Two methods are used in this study to train and evaluate the three selected ANN models:

- Full database: The model is trained on a split of 90 % of the overall data and tested on the remaining 10 %.
- All except one prototype: The model is trained over eight prototypes and is tested on the remaining one. The advantage of this method is to test the capacity of the model to predict the thermal performance of new geometry.

4.1. Classification model

i. Full database

In order to assess the performance of the classification model (Model 1) after identifying the best set of hyperparameters, the confusion matrix presented in Figure 3a) is used to visualize the distribution of correct and incorrect classifications on the testing set. For more interpretable visual results, the normalized confusion matrix is presented in Figure 3b); it depicts the percentage of correct and incorrect labeled points over the total number of labels.

Figure 3: a) confusion matrix and b) normalized confusion matrix.

The overall classification performance is reflected in the value of F1-score, the precision, and the recall of the pulsating category. These values are reported in Table 5 to evaluate the predictive performance of Model 1 for ten different data folds. It is shown that not only the predictive scores are high (95-97 %), but also the ratio of the standard deviation over the mean score values is low (1.1 %) for the F1-score. This ratio is known as the variation coefficient, and such a small value indicates that Model 1 performs well in predicting the operation class of PHP (Pulsation/conduction) regardless of the choice of training and test sets.

Table 5: Evaluation of the performance of Model 1 using F1-score, recall, and precision of the Pulsation category (10 folds of data)

	Mean value [%]	Standard deviation (10 folds) [%]	Variation coefficient [%]
F1-score	96.35	1.06	1.1
Recall	97.05	-	-
Precision	95.65	-	-

ii. All except one prototype:

As explained earlier in this section, training Model 1 on eight prototypes and evaluating its performance by predicting the operating mode of the remaining prototype could be a good indicator of how the model would perform for a new geometry. Therefore, the F1-score, recall, and precision of the pulsation category for each prototype are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Comparison of scores in predicting each prototype

The classification model performs very well predicting prototypes 1, 2, 6, 7, and 8, with the three scores above 80 %. However, this does not apply to prototypes 4 and 5, where most records fall in the conduction category, nor for prototypes 3 and 9, the longest among other prototypes ($L_{tot} = 1.245$ and 1.445 meters, respectively). Thus, excluding these prototypes with exceptional total lengths from the database make the model inexperienced in predicting such lengths. However, once included, the model will gain more experience and predict better thermal resistance of prototypes with similar exceptional geometries.

4.2. Regression models

i. Full database

In order to verify the accuracy of the best regression models, ten data groups are randomly selected using cross-validation. The mean values and standard deviations of $RMSE$ and R^2 are plotted in Figure 5a) and 5b) for the pulsation and conduction models, respectively.

Figure 5: Evaluation of the Regression models for conduction and pulsating data over ten folds by a) the root mean squared error and b) the R^2 score.

The pulsation model (Model 2) provides a $RMSE$ value of 0.07 K/W with a relatively small standard deviation of 0.0094 K/W (variation coefficient of 13.4%). The mean R^2 value is 0.8 with a standard deviation of 0.06 (variation coefficient of 7.5%). The slight variation coefficients of $RMSE$ and R^2 imply that the pulsation model delivers the best results regardless of the train/test data set.

However, this does not apply to the conduction model (Model 3) as the variation coefficients of $RMSE$ and R^2 are relatively high, about 21.2% and 65% , respectively.

The predicted thermal resistance using Models 2 and 3 are presented for each prototype versus the measured thermal resistance in Figure 6a) and 6b), respectively.

Figure 6: Predicted thermal resistance versus measured thermal resistance for a) the pulsation model (Model 2) and b) the conduction model (Model 3)

The better the prediction is, the closer the points would be on the bisector line. Therefore, the prediction results of Model 2 are satisfactory for all prototypes, whereas those of Model 3 perform better for prototypes 5 to 9. In order to verify the accuracy of the regression models, relative error (RE) and mean relative error (MRE) are calculated and presented for Models 2 and 3 in Figure 7a) and 7b), respectively.

$$RE = \frac{|y_{i\text{test}} - y_{i\text{pred}}|}{y_{i\text{test}}} \times 100 \% \quad (7)$$

$$MRE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N \frac{|y_{i\text{test}} - y_{i\text{pred}}|}{y_{i\text{test}}} \times 100 \% \quad (8)$$

Figure 7a) shows that for Model 2, the MRE of the test set is 11.48 %; The relative errors of only a few records of prototypes 1, 2, and 9 are above the MRE without exceeding 50 %. For Model 3, on the other hand (Figure 7b)), the mean relative error is 40.93%, and the relative errors of records are dispersed between 0-80%.

Figure 7: Relative error versus thermal resistance for each prototype for a) the pulsation model (Model 2) and b) the conduction model (Model 3). The solid lines represent the MRE.

ii. All except one prototype:

For prototypes 1 and 2, all the points correspond to the pulsating category, while for prototypes 4 and 5, most records operate in the conduction mode.

The mean relative errors in predicting each prototype for pulsating and conduction mode are presented in Figure 8a) and 8b), respectively.

Figure 8 : The mean relative errors (*MRE*) in predicting each prototype apart: a) for pulsating mode and b) for conduction mode

For pulsating data, the mean relative error (*MRE*) is below 40 % for all prototypes except for prototype 3 (*MRE* ~ 60%).

It seems that the conduction model overestimates the thermal performance of PHPs. Therefore, from an industrial point of view, it is essential to identify records that operate in conduction mode. However, the thermal resistance of these records is not very interesting, especially since PHPs are primarily conceived to operate in a pulsating mode. In other words, when the operating mode of a record is classified by Model 1 as ‘conduction,’ it will be automatically eliminated from the database created to optimize the performance of pulsating heat pipes. Therefore, the conduction Model 3 can help predict the upper limit of thermal resistance.

On the other hand, the evaluation of the pulsation Model 2 on the overall data and the prediction of the thermal performance of a new prototype prove that this neural network model can well predict the thermal resistance of a PHP operating in the pulsating mode.

5. Conclusion and further work

In this study, three artificial neural networks (ANN) algorithms were developed to evaluate the thermal performance of pulsating heat pipes.

The experimental data records were divided into 90/10 for training/testing. On this basis, the neural network models are used to predict the operating mode and the thermal resistance of PHPs.

The hyperparameters of the three ANN models are selected after a dedicated optimization was undertaken to achieve optimal accuracy.

For pulsating data, the predicted and actual values of the thermal resistance are in good coincidence, with an R^2 -value and an RMSE of 0.8 and 0.07 K/W, respectively. The average relative error (*MRE*) is calculated to better understand the accuracy of the network. The results show that the average relative error is 11.48%, indicating that the network can well predict the thermal resistance of a PHP. The relative error is higher for conduction data, with an average value of 40.93 %. Regardless, conduction results are less important as a PHP is primarily conceived to operate in a pulsating mode.

Thus, splitting data into pulsating and conduction and creating artificial neural network models based on the operating mode of a PHP has higher accuracy compared to the traditional numerical methods and produces results close to the verified data. The results of this study show that the three models of artificial

neural networks can predict the thermal performance of a PHP and thus provide an effective tool to characterize and optimize the PHP in various application synergies.

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